

Short communication

First records of *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) (Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae) in Lebanon and Israel

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Abstract. The first records of *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Megalonotini) for Lebanon and Israel are reported. Information on the known distribution of the species is summarized.

Key words: Hemiptera, *Lasiocoris crassicornis*, true-bugs, faunistics, distribution, new records, Israel, Lebanon, Palaearctic Region.

So far, the seed bug/rhynchrochromid *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) has been reported from Albania, Andorra, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, France, Greece (including the island of Crete), Italy (only from the islands of Sardinia and Sicily), North Macedonia, Romania, Russia (South-European part), Spain and Turkey (European part) in Europe; Algeria, Libya, Morocco and Tunisia in Northern Africa and Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Syria and Turkey (Asian part) in Asia (Protić 1987, as *Lasiocoris antennatus* Montandon, 1889; Péricart 1998, 2001; Linnavuori 2007; Ghahari & Moulet 2012).

However, the known distribution of the species has to be extended.

In the collection of the second author (P. Dioli) we found an interesting specimen from Lebanon, collected in Chouf, Barouk env., 1100 m, 04.–07.06.1999 (legit G. Magnani) (fig. 1). **It is the first record of *L. crassicornis* in Lebanon.**

On 09.03.2020, a specimen of *L. crassicornis* was found and photographed in Jerusalem by Omer Netanel. The photo was uploaded by Omer Netanel (pseudonym centaur) to the online database iNaturalist (Netanel 2020). **This is the first record of *L. crassicornis* in Israel** which has not been published in scientific publications, yet.

Generally similar to *Lasiocoris anomalus* (Kolenati, 1845), *L. crassicornis* differs by antennae shorter, 0.50 times as long as the body; the articles II and III widened from the base to the top, thicker, especially III, covered with much denser black pubescence. Body length: 6.4–7.5 mm (Péricart 1998).

Fig. 1. Specimens of *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) from Lebanon (left) and *Lasiocoris anomalus* (Kolenati, 1845) from Sicily/Italy (right). (Photo: Paride Dioli).

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Received: 23 March 2020

Accepted: 4 May 2020